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#STI22GRX

Exploring innovation studies through a blurb lenses: A textmetric approach to journal positioning

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Abstract

This paper presents a latent semantic analysis that mines for themes and context in journals’ “blurbs”, i.e., the peripheral, but official, content published as front-matter of academic outlets or at their official websites when describing the aims and scope. We take this qualitative raw material, an under-utilised source, for enhancing a scientometric approach to journals, or “journalytics” as we shorthand it. Taking innovation studies as an area of focus, we go through a corpus of evidence assembled from 20 top journals (over 50% in FT50 list). This set of journals is found to be organised around four clusters: “Innovation and technology”; “Sectoral studies”; “Organisational theory”; and “Strategic management”. Given the specific structure of the field, where *Research Policy* is the oldest and more prominent of the “flying geese” innovation-oriented outlets, we generated a semantic-sensitive table-rank in which six journals we found to have over 80% similarity, including *Industrial and Corporate Change*. We conclude that this textmetric strategy validates, complements, and, indeed, supplements other approaches (namely, bibliometrics-driven ones), thereby contributing to the portfolio of methodologies through which researchers and science policy analysts can systematically understand journals’ agendas, assess their relative positioning and standing, and frame their choices.

Keywords

scientometrics, metadata, innovation studies, journalytics, science indicators

Introduction

Understanding the aims and scope of academic journals is important for both substantive and instrumental reasons. For analysts of the science system, the mapping and measurement of journals’ standing is an instrumental perspective to shed light into the actual institutions

channelling the outputs of the research enterprise (Altbach & Wit, 2018; Evans, 2013). For authors, the rapid growth of scientific literature and research topics makes the task of determining where to submit their contributions harder and harder (Freeman, 1969; Mackey, Shah, Miyachi, Short, & Clauson, 2019; Moravcsik, 1975). For policymakers, who have to look for findings and to care for the visibility of research, the challenges are likewise daunting (May, 1997; Reale et al., 2018; Sooryamoorthy, 2020). We specifically advance (and implement) a methodology to compare (and order) journals by making use of their meta-materials through the deployment of text mining techniques.

The rapid progress and development of science created a demand for methods to measure and explain its growth. Whereas displacing the journal impact factor (JIF) from its dominant role has not yet happened, at least some effort can be invested into enriching the pluralism of journal indicators (for alternatives to the JIF see Larivière & Sugimoto, 2019; Rafols, Leydesdorff, O'Hare, Nightingale, & Stirling, 2012), namely through content-based and algorithmic subject categorisation and comparisons (see Rafols & Leydesdorff, 2009; Rousseau, Zhang, & Hu, 2019).

The novelty of our contribution, which does not rely on “classic” records (say, papers or references) or web 2.0 sources (like social media or other digital trails) is two-fold. First, we shift the focus from the research piece (the publication) to the research vehicle (the journal), that is, instead of the *product* we study the *platform* that distributes the research outputs. Second, we make use not of the materials inherent to scientific practice (say, the academic content) but instead of auxiliary information (i.e., the marketing and advertising corpus deployed for institutional promotion).

The field of innovation studies is taken here as the source ground for our empirical analysis. This area of study is committed to the understanding of the factors, processes and effects of science, technology and innovation phenomena. It is also a multidisciplinary enterprise and an intellectual project geared toward drawing practical insights that can be applied to management and policy (Caraça, Lundvall, & Mendonça, 2009; Fagerberg, Martin, & Andersen, 2013; Martin, 2019). For being an emergent field with a strong firm-centric focus in the early years and for nurturing a broader perspective later on with a greater emphasis on the environment in which knowledge actors operate (Castaldi & Mendonça, 2022), it offers itself both as a cohesive and diverse field to determine how journals differentiate and position when presenting themselves as vehicles for publishing.

This paper is organised as follows. In section 2, we introduce the research method. In section 3, we briefly describe the innovation studies sample and how data was acquired while, in section 4, we go through the content analysis and appraise the results. Finally, section 5 presents a critical synthesis.

Journalytics and research design

By tapping into “meta-knowledge” (i.e., the information about information that comes from “the critical scrutiny of what is known, how, and by whom”; Evans and Foster, 2011, p. 721), increased possibilities come forward so as to identify patterns in the scientific system. For our purposes, the synopsis that accompanies journals is taken as the data source. This material is particularly rich since this text has both descriptive (information, i.e., what is the journal about) and persuasive (advertising, i.e., why stakeholders should be attracted to it) purposes (see Costa, 2020). For purposes of expediency, we will call “blurbs” to these self-referential materials, a shorthand we take from the promotional briefs that are used in manuscripts to entice book

agents to go through the whole work or on the back of finished books to catch the attention of potential readers (Hall, 2016).

Our approach brings forward the (quantitative) indicators that can be derived from such textual evidence (blurbs). The methodology adds to the toolbox of relevant materials and metrics which are used to understand journals. For this purpose, we apply to the field of innovation studies a journalytics approach, a term elected here to refer to data science and statistical techniques devoted to assessing journals' profile. This could be implemented by turning the tools of scientometrics more explicitly on journals, i.e., setting up an empirical inquiry of journals as a phenomenon. In what follows we proceed to establish a perimeter of innovation-oriented outlets; and identify the blurbs from which a corpus can be built. The steps are shown in Figure 1 and are comprehensively described in the following sections.

Figure 1. Deriving scientometric value from blurbs: A methodology.

Innovation studies: the field and its journals

The key titles in innovation studies

As shown by Fagerberg and Verspagen (2009), who approached practitioners to identify their organisations and institutions, innovation studies have grown with contributions from several thousand academics worldwide. As the authors point out, the most central channel on innovation is *Research Policy*, launched in 1972 by Christopher Freeman, also the first director of Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU), established in 1966 in the University of Sussex. This journal, which is the oldest of a "flying geese" formation of the innovation-focused journals, will be taken here as benchmark for the field. Adopting an exploratory design, we will limit our analysis to a small, but influential, sample of innovation studies journals. Fagerberg et al. (2012) identified a set of 20 leading journals publishing on innovation studies (Table 1 summarises their features).

Table 1. List of innovation-oriented journals.

Journal	Subject area ¹	Quartile (* if FT50)	Launch	Publisher
<i>Academy of Management Journal (AMJ)</i>	Business	Q1*	1958	Academy of Management
<i>Academy of Management Review (AMR)</i>	Business	Q1*	1976	Academy of Management
<i>Administrative Science Quarterly (ASQ)</i>	Arts and Humanities; Social Sciences	Q1*	1956	SAGE Publications
<i>Cambridge Journal of Economics (CJE)</i>	Economics	Q1	1977	Oxford University Press
<i>Human Relations (HR)</i>	Arts and Humanities; Business; Social Sciences	Q1*	1947	SAGE Publications
<i>Industrial and Corporate Change (ICC)</i>	Economics	Q1	1992	Oxford University Press
<i>International Journal of Technology Management (IJTM)</i>	Business; Computer Science; Engineering; Social Sciences	Q1	1986	Interscience Enterprises
<i>Journal of International Business Studies (JIBS)</i>	Business; Economics.	Q1*	1970	Palgrave Macmillan
<i>Journal of Management Studies (JMS)</i>	Business	Q1*	1964	John Wiley & Sons
<i>Management Science (MS)</i>	Business; Decision Sciences	Q1*	1954	Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences
<i>Organization Science (OSc)</i>	Business	Q1*	1990	Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences
<i>Organization Studies (OSt)</i>	Business	Q1*	1980	SAGE Publications
<i>R&D Management (RDM)</i>	Business	Q1	1970	John Wiley & Sons
<i>Regional Studies (RS)</i>	Environmental Science; Social Sciences	Q1	1967	Taylor & Francis
<i>Research Policy (RP)</i>	Business; Decision Sciences; Engineering	Q1*	1971	Elsevier
<i>Small Business Economics (SBE)</i>	Business; Economics.	Q1	1989	Springer

¹ Some subject areas descriptors are shortened from their coded as follow: 1) Business: Business, Management and Accounting; 2) Economics: Economics, Econometrics and Finance.

<i>Strategic Management Journal (SMJ)</i>	Business	Q1*	1980	John Wiley & Sons
<i>Technology Analysis & Strategic Management (TASM)</i>	Business; Decision Sciences	Q2	1989	Taylor & Francis
<i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change (TFSC)</i>	Business; Psychology	Q1	1969	Elsevier
<i>Technovation (Tec)</i>	Business; Engineering	Q1	1981	Elsevier

Source: The list of journals from Fagerberg et al. (2012). Scimago descriptors as of 2020.

Note: * referring to presence in the Financial Times Top 50 journal ranking. The FT50 journals list can be found at: <https://www.ft.com/content/3405a512-5cbb-11e1-8f1f-00144feabdc0>.

Blurbs text retrieval and corpus building

Journals' homepages display several special features that can instruct us about journals' thematic focus. Although journals' self-description is present in all journal's webpages, for some outlets a short description may be found in the home page, as the main text, while in others the self-description is found under sections like "Aims and Scope" or "About". A total of 2,111 words were retrieved. Blurb size varies considerably across journals (TFSC being the smallest with 31 words and OSc the largest with 281) and appears to be heavily influenced by publisher policy (space awarded to this information on the websites).

Pre-processing blurbs for analytical assessment

For the ultimate goal of analysing the self-presentation materials, the pre-processing steps were also applied to the blurb's texts. The text segmentation divided the original text into words (Hinterberger et al., 2009), word pieces that are trivial or merely auxiliary, called "stopwords" were removed (Schofield, Magnusson, & Mimno, 2017) and the Porter (1980) algorithm was applied to reduce morphological variants to a root/base word.

Results and discussion

Analysing the blurbs: The similarity of journal agendas

Different approaches are used to measure texts similarity. The term-based similarity models treat each string (or document) as a set of tokens (stem words). The main characteristic of term-based similarity is the use of the overlap of two documents as likeness quantification. In this study, blurbs contents are matched through the cosine similarity because it is calculated using only the dot product and magnitude of each vector. Therefore, it is affected only by the terms both vectors have in common. The angle between two vectors defines cosine similarity. As $\cos \theta$ may range between $[0,1]$, 0 means that the two vectors, say x and y , are orthogonal (uncorrelated) and, thus, there is not semantic relation between the two texts but if $\cos \theta$ is near to 1, their vectors are closer, and therefore their contents are more similar (Günther, Dudschig, & Kaup, 2014). The cosine measure of the angle between two non-zero vectors of an inner product space may be defined as:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{x \cdot y}{\|x\| \|y\|} \quad (1)$$

Although vectors could have lots of attributes with frequency zero, it does not over-penalise content's overlap for non-common terms (Landauer, Laham, & Foltz, 1998). It has been

proposed as a robust metric for scoring the similarity between two strings by Tata and Patel (2007). Similar documents can be grouped as clusters. The hierarchical clustering will make it possible to generate more clusters with more similar documents within or fewer clusters with more heterogenous units.

To understand the relationships between journal blurbs, the results of cosine blurbs vectors within the semantic space are illustrated in Figure 2, where darker colours indicate closer blurbs. There were no white spaces found, indicating that no blurbs were semantic opposites, supporting the journal sample coherence as a whole.

Figure 2. Heatmap and dendrogram of the cosine similarity between journals.

Note: Nearest neighbour (or single linkage clustering) method.

Clear clusters emerge based on the semantic proximity between blurbs. Around the heatmap, the dendrogram illustrates the arrangement of the clusters produced by the corresponding analyses (i.e., hierarchical clustering). Each cluster was furthermore labelled according to the common topics encompassed; a content-explicit representation is displayed in Figure 3. To suggest labelling solutions, the journals' blurbs from each group were analysed and a wordcloud computed.

Figure 4. Blurbs' cosine similarity between Research Policy and all other journals.

In the first positions, it is possible to identify the six journals previously identified in “Innovation and technology” cluster (marked in black). All these journals have a high degree of similarity, above 0.8 (Abbas, Ferrari, Shatnawi, Enoiu, & Saadatmand, 2021; Nugraheni, Widodo, & Sari, 2022; Qurashi, Holmes, & Johnson, 2020). Other tiers were delineated following a criterion of discrepancy: the existence of two large drops in the cosine were found. As a result, and besides the core group, we posit the presence of three tiers of journals. First, the second-tier journals still seem to exhibit a substantive affinity to innovation concepts and phenomenon. This set of journals is well above 0.5, a threshold that is believed to separate strong from weak similarities (Oghbaie and Zanjireh, 2018). Second, the below-core tiers are not as neatly patterned as the first tier since each has journals that belong to several clusters previously identified (symbols are used to make this visually evident). For instance, the “Strategic management” journals are found spread across all the three lower tiers.

Third, aligning the ranking obtained from a conventional impact metric like the H-index scores achieved by journals with the cosine similarities, it is possible to notice the rearranged positions. Figure 5 illustrates how journals change their ranking position according to the method of comparison (H-index vs cosine similarity). The spearman correlation shows to be of -0.6516, with a p-value of 0.0018, suggesting a significant and negative association between both ranking approaches. That is, the outcome of this analysis does not simply replicate some well-known stylized facts of the field of innovation studies; the comparison of our semantic-sensitive results (showing a hierarchy of journals explicitly oriented to innovation) to a conventional, bibliometric-driven ranking of journals (in which strong preferences for the innovation agenda are not picked up).

Figure 5. Journals' position for H-index and cosine similarity.

Note: The journals identified in the “Innovation and technology” cluster are in black.

Discussion and conclusions

In this contribution, we articulate an argument to expand the realm of scientometrics and bring in journals more explicitly to the fore. Our analysis of the journals' blurb evidence has generated novel insights about the outlets more focused on innovation studies and pointers that suggest this textmetric approach is of potential use for future research and in other areas. In particular, practitioners, including information scientists, administrators that monitor productivity and progress, and policy-makers who are concerned with the rhythm and direction of the science system, may benefit from efforts to open the academic journal black-box.

Taking advantage of short self-promotional contents, referred here as blurbs, and by applying cosine similarity we are able to distinguish unacknowledged journal profiles and positionings: four clusters of journals emerged that have not been recognised before: “Innovation and technology”, “Sectoral economics”, “Organisational theory”, and “Strategic management”. Along the way, our research was able to validate the (heterogeneous) innovation-friendly journal sample we departed from and identify seven journals that belong to the core group of innovation studies (the “Innovation and technology” cluster, which is where *Research Policy* and *Industrial and Corporate Change* are located).

By establishing and taking a journal as the benchmark in innovation-related research (*Research Policy*, is the first of a set of innovation-focused journals to enter the “academic marketplace”), we can also propose a semantic alternative to conventional metrics, i.e., a novel “soft” ordering of journals which can be used to guide journal-paper matching. This discourse-driven or substance-sensitive mapping of journals is quite different from the usual, citation-dependent rankings methods. We find that the “Innovation and technology” journals, where *Industrial and Corporate Change* is included, are the closest ones to *Research Policy*, followed by a hierarchy of other journals not connected to a particular journal cluster or correlated with impact factor.

The evidence we obtained suggests it is possible to adopt a “journalytics” approach to scientometrics; this can be done by considering easy-to-read narrative meta-information (the small promotional materials we dubbed blurbs) to enhance our understanding of journals (see Santos and Mendonça, 2022). The results found for the innovation studies field suggest that the methodology can also be useful to comprehend, compare and classify serial literature channels, i.e., the journals, in other academic fields. More should, and can, be done in the future about journals as objects of analysis and modern platforms of research distribution.

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